

ISic3077

I.Sicily inscription 3077

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

decree (?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Viale Teocrito

Coordinates

4. [-----]ΣKEY [---]
5. [-----]Γ[---]ΙΛΝΟ [---]
6. [-----]ΤΑΣ [---]
7. [-----]ΛΟΥ [---]
8. [-----]ΕΤ. [---]
9. [-----]ΘΥ [---]
10. [-----]ΛΕ [---]
- 11.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 653656

PHI 329770

PHI 337258

Bibliography

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